

Performance Analysis of Dental and Oral Therapists in Efforts to Manage Dental Services during the Covid-19 Pandemic in Garut Regency

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ABSTRACT: Based on Garut Regency staffing information in 2020 that the performance target of dental and oral therapist employees during the Covid-19 pandemic was almost 53% in the moderate category so that the performance of dental and oral therapist employees decreased in the performance category compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic. Objective: To determine the performance of dental and oral therapists in the management of dental services during the Covid-19 pandemic. Research Methods: Using descriptive analytic design with qualitative methods with spearman rho test on dental and oral therapists in the work area of Garut Regency by using data collection by questionnaire with the help of google forms. Results: The results showed that the performance of dental and oral therapists during Covid-19 in the Garut Regency area was still classified as having moderate criteria of 71.23% and efforts to manage dental services during the Covid-19 period showed good criteria of 86.30%. Conclusion: The performance of dental and oral therapists during the Covid-19 period in Garut Regency was classified as moderate, while in the management of dental services the criteria were good with $p \text{ value} = 0.652 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that this study is not significant.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, Dental Service Management, Performance Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19) is a disease caused by Novel Coronavirus or now called SARS-CoV-2 which is a new type of virus that has never been identified before in humans. Common signs and symptoms of Covid-19 infection include symptoms of acute respiratory distress, other symptoms of fever, cough and runny nose, to severe cases it can cause pneumonia, acute respiratory syndrome, kidney failure and even death. Clinical manifestations appear within 2 to 14 days after exposure. Until now, it is believed that transmission of Covid-19 is through droplets and direct contact, unless there is a medical procedure that triggers aerosols (such as cardiopulmonary resuscitation, dental examinations such as the use of ultrasonic scalers and high speed air driven, nose and throat examinations, use of a nebulizer and swab collection) which can trigger the risk of airborne transmission [1–4].

Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19), is still a global problem. December 2019, Wuhan, China became the first country to be exposed to the Covid-19 virus. Approximately 10 months of the increase in the number of cases of Covid-19 sufferers continues to increase, monitoring from the Worldometers data center as of September 28, 2020 recorded that around 33.57 million people were exposed to the Covid-19 virus, Indonesia is ranked 24th out of 25 countries with Covid-19 cases. 19 in the world with a total of 278,722 people, as of July 2020 around 295 medical personnel were exposed to Covid-19 and 23 people died. The death rate for health workers exposed to Covid-19 in Indonesia is the highest in Southeast Asia, which is 2.4% [5–7]. Based on information, that in West Java there were 56 health workers who died due to exposure to Covid-19. Meanwhile, there are 620 health workers in Garut Regency who were exposed to Covid-19 during the Covid-19 pandemic. The personnel in question are nurses to doctors. Based on information from the Garut Regency Covid-19 task force, there are around 23 health workers who have been confirmed positive for Covid-19.

The Covid-19 pandemic cannot be ascertained when it will end, while the community still needs health services, especially in first-level health facilities, especially dental and oral health services. The WHO survey states that the Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted public access to health services. Efforts are needed to adjust dental and oral health services to prevent transmission which can save the lives of patients and dentists. During the Covid-19 pandemic, facilities the first level of health (in this case the public health center) must continue to provide dental and oral health services to the community by following the rules contained in the applicable Covid-19 prevention and control guidelines, paying attention to the rules of Infection Prevention and Control (PPI) and physical distancing in order to break the chain of transmission. The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic has almost been felt by all people in the world with

the exception of the dental and oral therapist profession. At present, dental and oral therapists have their own challenges in providing dental health care services with the risk that dental and oral therapists can become victims of exposure to Covid-19. The high physical and psychological impact that befell dental therapists during the Covid-19 pandemic will certainly affect the performance of dental therapists in carrying out their duties and functions, dental and oral therapists themselves are one of the health workers who are most vulnerable to exposure to the corona virus. According to Rundungan the results of his research show that motivation, work ability, work experience and facilities or facilities greatly affect dental and oral health services [8–11].

Based on staffing information from Garut Regency in 2020 that the performance target of dental and oral therapist employees during the Covid-19 pandemic was almost around 53% in the sufficient category so that the performance of dental and oral therapist employees decreased in the performance category compared to before the Covid-19 pandemic.

METHODOLOGY

This research design uses analytical descriptive, which is a method to get in-depth data, a data that contains meaning and can significantly affect the substance of the research [12]. Researchers want to analyze the performance of dental and oral therapists in an effort to manage dental and oral services during the Covid-19 pandemic on duty at the public health center or hospital in Garut Regency. The sampling technique in this study using purposive sampling technique, as many as 73 people. The research variables in this study are the dependent variable: performance of dental and oral therapists and the independent variable: efforts to manage dental and oral health services. The data collection instrument used in this study was a questionnaire, consisting of a questionnaire about the performance of dental therapists with 5 questions and a questionnaire about efforts to manage dental services during the COVID-19 pandemic with 10 questions. Data analysis using spearman test.

RESULT

Table 1. Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics

Respondent characteristics	Total	
	n	%
Gender		
Male	15	20.5
Female	58	79.5
Total	73	100
Dental service agency		
Public health center	66	90.5
Government hospital	4	5.4
Private hospital	2	2.7
Dental clinic	1	1.4
Total	73	100

Table 1 shows that the number of female respondents was more than male, namely 58 respondents (79.5%) and the working in a dental health service agency at the public health center was 66 respondents (90.5%).

Table 2. Frequency distribution based on efforts to manage dental and oral health services

Performance	Total	
	n	%
Good	21	28.8
Moderate	52	71.2
Low	0	0
Total	73	100

Table 2 shows that the percentage value of performance with the highest criteria moderate category as many as 52 respondents with a percentage of 71.23%

Table 3. Frequency distribution based on Dental and Oral Therapist Performance

Manage dental and oral health services	Total	
	n	%
Good	63	86.3
Moderate	10	13.7
Low	0	0
Total	73	100

Table 3 shows that the efforts to manage dental and oral health services with the highest criteria in the good category were 63 respondents with a percentage of 86.30%.

Table 4. Correlation of performance of dental and oral therapists with efforts to manage dental and oral health services

Spearman test	p-value	Correlation coefficient
	0.625	0.054

Table 4 shows that the Spearman statistical test analysis with p value = 0.625 > 0.05, meaning that there is no significant relationship between the performance of dental and oral therapists with the management of dental and oral health services during the Covid-19 period in Garut Regency.

DISCUSSION

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by a person in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. The performance of dental and oral therapists in the Garut area during the Covid-19 pandemic in carrying out dental and oral services has been implemented in accordance with standard operating procedures. The purpose of this study was to analyze the performance of dental and oral therapists and efforts to manage dental services during the Covid-19 period.

The results of the research on the performance of dental and oral therapists mostly had moderate criteria, reaching 71.23%, namely as many as 52 respondents. This happens because dental and oral therapists are still not compliant in applying the standard operating procedures for Covid-19 services, namely in terms of officers carrying out hand washing procedures properly, officers pay little attention to the importance of using medical gowns, using disposable personal protective equipment, sterilization. tools and cleanliness of the work environment that is not paid attention to. So if it is ignored, the dental and oral therapist is at high risk of being exposed to the Covid-19 virus. This proves that in terms of knowledge, they actually have mastered it, but in reality, in the field, dental and oral therapists still ignore the Covid-19 service protocol. The research above is in line with the research conducted by Rundungan and Asmi in their research showing that work ability greatly affects dental and oral health services so that support and attention from the government are needed to improve the performance of dental and oral therapists [11,13].

The results of the research on the management of dental and oral health services with good criteria reached 86.30%, namely 63 respondents. The results of the data above for dental and oral therapists in terms of efforts to manage dental services during the Covid-19 pandemic illustrate good results. This proves that dental and oral therapists are seen in terms of skills and knowledge that are competent. This research is also in line with research conducted by Masitahsari and Soleha in an effort to improve the performance of health workers during the Covid-19 period, it is hoped that the government can pay special attention, especially in the provision of PPE and provide additional incentives to health workers on duty. considering the magnitude of the risks they face both physically and psychologically [6,14].

The results of Spearman's statistical test analysis with p value = 0.652 > 0.05 so that the performance of dental and oral therapists during the Covid-19 period in Garut Regency with the management of dental and oral health services in this study was not significant.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that there is a no significant relationship between the performance of dental and oral therapists with the management of dental and oral health services during the Covid-19 period in Garut Regency.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author hereby declares no conflict of interest

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